

DEVELOPING READING SKILLS THROUGH ACTIVE READING TECHNIQUES

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Annotation: This article focuses on developing students' reading skills in learning foreign languages. Particularly, the investigation determines the role of reading skills and importance of active reading in teaching foreign languages. The aim of the article is consideration the significance of developing learners' active reading skills in teaching English particularly effective activities used in different stages of teaching reading to foreign language learners.

Key words: Active reading, Highlighting, Read Aloud / Think Aloud, Making Predictions, to look for 'signposts', to draw and sketch, clarifying;

Presently in the process of globalization, knowing foreign languages becomes necessary as people can't communicate with each other without knowing them. Besides, in modern society English is becoming an essential component of professional training. Specialists of various fields want to obtain a higher level of language proficiency, because it affects the successful solution of issues and professional growth. In many professions there is a need to establish contacts with foreign partners and communicate professionally, that's modern methodology worked out innovative methods which help learners and teachers to choose the most effective and suitable ways of effective learning.

Having discussed the term "reading" and stages of teaching reading we have understood that reading is complex process to organize and teach. In order to engage whole class to the lesson it is demanded from the teacher to choose correct and effective way of teaching, create the atmosphere of surveying, questioning, involving to the text completely and actively. One of the basic tools of teaching reading skillfully is active reading process including a great number of techniques to get involved in the lesson.

Active reading takes place when students are proactively involved in the reading of a text. Active reading is about more than reading words in black and white and answering questions afterwards. Student engagement is important in order to optimize learning, so when you, as the teacher, get your students involved in what they are reading, they are more likely to better understand the meaning within the text.

Active reading simply means reading something with a determination to understand and evaluate it for its relevance to your needs. Simply reading and re-reading the material isn't an effective way to understand and learn. Actively and critically engaging with the content can save your time. Most of study books and websites include in-text questions and self-assessed questions. It is an effective way of teaching reading using these as built-in cues to make learning active.

Active reading is simply a means of reading a book with the deliberate intent to learn and apply something from it. Active reading involves reading a book *with* a student rather

than reading a book *to* a student. This evidence-based approach improves students' language skills, vocabulary, and ability to understand what they read on their own. Active reading works with children, adults at any ages. In active reading, an adult shares a picture book with a child and provides the child with multiple opportunities to talk about and engage with the pictures, words and ideas in the book. The adult's role is to be an active listener, ask questions, and get the child talking and thinking about the book or any type of text.

Active reading skills can be developed by the following ways:

- ❖ Survey- what can I learn from the text?
- ❖ Before reading skim the material:
 - ✓ Skim the table of contents and find three to five main ideas that will be presented in the text.
 - ✓ Pay attention to names, headings and subheadings.
 - ✓ Look at the captions under images, tables, diagrams and maps.
 - ✓ Pay particular attention to the introductory and final paragraphs, which often contain a summary of the text.
- ❖ Question- what do I hope to learn from the text
- ❖ Before reading a section, formulate questions and do the following:
 - ✓ Rephrase headings into questions.
 - ✓ Look whether the author has formulated questions at the beginning or end of the section.
 - ✓ Recall what you already know about the topic and what you still want to learn about it.
- ❖ Read-look for answers to your questions
- ❖ Read captions under images and diagrams. Pay attention to highlighted information.
- ❖ Be open-minded – pay attention to new ideas and differing opinions.
- ❖ Stop and reread difficult and unclear parts.
- ❖ Recite – consider what you want to remember from the information obtained
- ❖ Think about what you've read and summarize the main ideas expressed in the text.
- ❖ If you realize there is something you have not fully understood, reread that section.
- ❖ Take notes, expressing ideas in your own words.
- ❖ Recall- reread your notes and link the information with your own experience
- ❖ After reading the whole text, reread your own notes and pay attention to the main ideas and connections between the ideas.
- ❖ Link what you have learned with your own experience and other sources of information.

There are some common strategies that can be used to keep students engaged in the reading of the text.

Highlighting - this will only work if you demonstrate proper highlighting techniques for your students. It is a pointless strategy if you are simply handing your students a highlighter and telling them to highlight the important information as they read. If students do not understand what important information looks like, they will likely highlight everything they come across as they are reading. For example, you may want to start by having students highlight the title of the selection, letting them know that the title gives the reader clues

regarding what the story will be about. As students are highlighting, they will have to pay close attention to the reading, thus remaining actively involved in the process.

Read Aloud / Think Aloud - as the teacher, you will probably want to show your students how to do this, so that you can be sure that they are using the strategy correctly. It may be beneficial for you to start with a series of short passages or articles, making sure that each student has his own copy.

Making Predictions - this strategy is used as the student is actively reading a text, and can be used with long or short passages. When students are making predictions, they are guessing what will happen next in the story. For example, in the story of the Three Pigs, the wolf visits each of the pigs in an attempt to get into their homes. After the wolf visits the first pig's home and blows the house down, the teacher may ask students "What do you think will happen next when the wolf visits the next pig's home?" The teacher is asking the students to make a prediction. As the students continue to read, they will find out whether their prediction was correct.

It is teacher's responsibility to have his / her students try these techniques to make their reading active. There are also some sub-strategies which can be used by a teacher to make students reading more active and efficient.

To underline or highlight key words and phrases while reading. When returning to it later on, it can easily be seen which points are identified as vital. Be selective - too much highlighting won't help.

To make annotations in the margin to summarize points, raise questions, challenge what has been read, jot down examples can be helpful to remember the content better. This takes more thought than highlighting.

To read critically by asking questions of the text. Who wrote it? When? Who is the intended audience? Does it link with other material studied in the module? Why do you think it was written? Is it an excerpt from a longer piece of text?

To test themselves by reading for half an hour, putting the text away and jotting down the key points from memory. Go back to the text to fill in gaps.

To look for 'signposts' that help students understand the text - phrases like 'most importantly', 'in contrast', 'on the other hand'.

To explain what they have read to groups, friends, peers. **To make outlines, flow charts, or diagrams that help students to map and to understand ideas visually. To read each paragraph carefully and then determine "what it says" and "what it does." Answer "what it says" in only one sentence.** Represent the main idea of the paragraph in their own words. To answer "what it does," describe the paragraph's purpose within the text, such as "provides evidence for the author's first main reason" or "introduces an opposing view."

To write a summary of an essay or chapter in their own words. Do this in less than a page. Capture the essential ideas and perhaps one or two key examples. This approach offers a great way to be sure that the students know what the reading really says or is about. **To teach what they have learned to someone else.** Research clearly shows that teaching is one of the most effective ways to learn. If students try to explain aloud what they have been studying, (1) they'll transfer the information from short-term to long-term memory, and (2) they'll quickly discover what they understand and what they don't.

To draw and sketch- No matter what type of information you're reading, visual learners can always create a mind map, a Venn diagram, a sketch, or a timeline to represent the information. Start by taking a clean sheet of paper and creating a visual representation of the book or chapter you're covering. You'll be amazed by the difference this will make for retaining and remembering details.

Clarifying - as students engage in questioning the text, they may need to clarify or clear up some of the questions that remain unanswered. Clarifying may involve students being able to answer the basic who, what, when, where, why and how questions as they are reading. It may also require students to answer more higher-order questions that require them to be able to examine the text beyond the basics. Higher order questions are those that may ask the students to analyze, create, describe or evaluate specific parts of the story. A student's ability to answer these types of questions will require them to first be able to understand what they have read.

Students may also need to re-read portions of the text and restate them, or the teacher may need to guide students through the critical thinking process in order to help them develop the ability to clarify with accuracy.

Summarizing - another active reading strategy is having students summarize what they have read in order to check comprehension. Summarizing is when students put the content of the text into their own words. The summary should include key information from the text but not be so long that it exceeds the length of the text. For example, a five-sentence passage should not be summarized in five sentences, as it defeats the purpose of the summary. A five-sentence passage should require no more than two sentences, and should be sufficient enough to allow the writer to explain the gist of the reading. Students often have difficulty with this strategy because they either leave out important information, or their summaries are too long. Teachers will likely need to model this particular strategy so that students can become proficient with it.

Much of what we have said already is contained within a well known technique for actively engaging with and extracting meaning from content - SQ3R. It is good for revision as well as reading something for the first time. 'SQ3R' stands for the five steps involved.

- **Skim** - through the text quickly to get an overall impression.
- **Question**- If you are reading it for a particular purpose (for example, to answer an assignment), ask yourself how it helps. Also ask questions of the text: Who? What? Where? When? How?
- **Read**- Read the text in a focused and fairly speedy way.
- **Remember** - Test your memory - but don't worry if you can't remember much.
- **Review** - Read the text in more detail, taking notes. Use your own words.

Active reading techniques can help students stay focused and retain more information, but it's a skill that takes work to develop. These are some strategies to help teachers get started right away. The article has proved that approaches to the teaching reading have changed considerably in recent years as insights from research and theory have prompted the reconsideration of what it means to teach these important components of second language proficiency.

In conclusion we can say that active reading techniques make the EFL classes informative, motivating and effective even though there may be different factors which cause

problems sometimes. This means that teacher should be very careful in conducting the reading classes paying attention to possible problematic situations.

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